

SMS-BASED VOTING SYSTEM FOR CRISIS PRONE AREAS IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The process of casting a vote in Nigeria is commonly associated with high risk factors such as violence. This singular exercise poses a lot of threat to life and security. In order to reduce these perceived risk factors, this paper proposes the use of SMS based voting system. The SMS based voting system allows voters to cast their vote from the comfort of their home or pre-selected secured area. The system is designed with a third party application programming interface to configure an automated voting result collation, load balancing and concurrency on a real time basis. In comparison with the current mode of voting currently used in Nigeria, the proposed method is cost effective, secured and highly reliable.

Keywords: Election violence, INEC, SMS voting, Nigeria

1. INTRODUCTION

Voting is a critical feature of any democratic process and is a vital expression of the peoples' power of choice (Robert, 2011). Voting is the most vital citizen participation in democracy as it can inherently facilitate the expression of general will. Voting is the strongest tool for expressing citizen content and exercising oversight over government bodies. Voting should not be understood as a mechanical process but as for having a creative capacity of its own as it provides for the unification of the people (Resanvallón, 2006).

According to the analysis by Ayeeni and Essan (2018), since 1998, the independent national electoral commission (INEC) has deployed several Information Communications Technologies (ICT) to improve the management and conduct of elections in Nigeria ranging from: the optical magnetic recognition (OMR) form which was introduced in 2003 to enable voters' registration to be done with a computer readable form; the Automatic Fingerprints Identification System (AFIS), introduced in 2003 along side

with OMR forms to reduce multiple registration; the Double Data Capture Machines (DDCM), introduced in 2007 to eliminate double registration, double voting and other identity related malpractices; INEC Voters Identification System (IVAS), a unique identification number incorporated into a smart card permanent voters card for each individual voter, introduced in 2007 for mainly voters' accreditation, and which helped to minimize incidences of multiple voting; and the Election Transparency Administration and Collation (e-TRAC) platform, a result collation website used from 2015 elections and upwards.

These aforementioned technologies were introduced by INEC to solve the problems of non-electronic voters' register, double/multiple registration, double/multiple voting, vote counting, result transmission, and result collation. None has been targeted to cater the needs of those in crisis ravaged areas like Benue State, Bornu State, Adamawa State, Yobe State, Plateau State, Nassarawa State and others. Unlike other people in some parts of the country,

citizens in these crisis prone areas are restricted from exercising their franchise by the day to day terror unleashed on them by lawless entities; and so would not have the confidence to appear at a designated place for voting. Hence, there is need for a system that allows them to remotely vote without the fear of molestation.

The aim of this study is to increase voters' participation in crisis prone areas of Nigeria. To achieve this, we developed and implemented an SMS based voting system with the added advantage of reducing multiple voting; eradication of the problem of misplaced result sheet; reduction of inherent possible intimidation and insecurity during voting; real-time counting of votes; and increased user participation.

2. RELATED WORK

Election violence is not a modern –day phenomenon starting with the 1994/95 election violence in the first republic (1960-1966); the 1997 election violence, in the second republic (1979-1983); the 1983 election in the third republic (1992-1993); and the 1999, 2003, 2007, 2011 and 2015 election violence of the present day fourth republic (1999-date) which have claimed over 800 lives. Regrettably, nothing serious have been done to forestall future re-occurrences since the elite and the politicians has resorted to it as a tool to either retain power or rustle power from the incumbent. In additional, the thousand of security personnel deployed during election, has not helped matters as most of these security agents have not been equipped with the right international practices (Ojo, 2018). Some causes of election violence are lack of internal democracy within political parties; inefficiency of the electoral commissions; inadequate security personnel; inadequate voter education; voters' bribery and rumor of rigging (Kalu and Gberevbie, 2018).

Unfortunately, election violence discourages citizen's participation in the political process as was recorded in 2011 and 2015 general elections were over 30 percentage (70 million) registered voters absconded from voting due to fear of violence. This voters' apathy portrays a threat to the sustainability of Nigerian democracy since these low turnout of voters does not reflect people's preferences (Sesan, 2012).

While Balogun (2013) defines electoral violence as the act of aggression that leads to inflicting injury on persons, destruction of properties and causing pandemonium within a given social

gathering, community or society; USIP (2018) narrowed their definition of electoral violence as a consequence of flawed processes that are further compromised (complicated) by the actions or inactions of the INEC or the security agents. Hence, the need for an enhanced voting system that will allow INEC to conduct transparent elections, as well as ensure the safety of voters irrespective of their locations.

The SMS based voting system is a voting system that allows voters to cast their votes from their comfortable locations by sending a SMS in a predefined format with a unique password and identification number in the comfort of their homes, providing secured and trustworthy e-voting services (Ofori-Dwumfuo & Paatey, 2011). The advancement in the mobile devices based on wireless sensor networks and web technologies which has given rise to this new application that will make voting process very easy and efficient. The SMS voting system will manage the voters' information while allowing them to exercise their voting rights. The system may incorporate all features of a normal voting system. It provides the tools for maintaining voters' details and the system counts the total number of votes for each contestant. There is a database which is maintained by the electoral commission body in which all the names of voters with complete information are stored both for present use or future use and analysis (Wildmaria,2010).

The over 2.4 billion active users of SMS across the globe and the need to provide a fast, secured and reliable system of voting has motivated several conferences and journals on electronic voting (e-voting). Ekwonwune, et al (2013) conducted a study using a structured questionnaire using a statistical descriptive research design. Their result showed that IT-based electoral management is less prone to election fraud and increases voters' participation when compared to the traditional paper based management.

Adewale, Ogundele and Adetumbi, (2009) proposed the use of eigenface technology for accrediting voters during elections. This face recognition system would require voters' facial identity to be stored during voters' registration; and later be verified during. Just like the case of law enforcement agents, the eigenface technology will only ensure voters' authentication; leaving out the confidentiality and the integrity of the votes and the result; the

reliability and accessibility of the system; and other security threats associated with voting. Alimi, Adegunodo, and Gambo (2009) identified the reliability of the system as a key determinant to the adoption of e-voting system and therefore proposed a cleanroom system of development that will ensure global standards during its design and development. Using the cleanroom design process developers of e-voting would focus on prevention of defects instead of its removal.

SMS based voting system machine developed by Warriar (2010) allows voters to cast their votes by sending SMS in a predefined format with a unique password and identification number in the comfort of their own homes. The voting machine receives the messages, decode the message and verify their pin and identification number, if both number matches, the voting machine will accept the vote, otherwise, the message is rejected by the machine. The voting system makes use of a pic micro controller and a GSM modem to receive messages from the voters. An LCD screen is used to display the final result. In this system, there is no security measure put in place to provide system integrity.

Cranor(2003) specified the requirements for both SMS voting system and e-voting using an

than the paper ballot system but little pitfall of electronic failure might occur with such system. Agbaye, Olugbenga, & Joshua (2006) developed an SMS based system that allows voters to vote using a specially registered SIM card. The paper also suggested two different security models - blind signature and elgamal encryption algorithm - to handle threats related to e-voting. However, this system will require the voters to visit their polling station and vote from INEC phones. No consideration was given to handling network overload since so many people will be voting within the same period; and no provision was made about the architecture of the proposed system and the component used for handling the SMS messages in order to ascertain the robustness of their system.

In a later presentation, the Oluwaranti, Olugboji, & Afolab (2010) SMS-based system, considered the possible network overload arising from application usage. Thus the authors integrated a 3rd party application programming interface (API) SMSLib. This is contrary to the AT+ set of commands used by some SMS systems. Instead of establishing constant connection with the modem and thereby causing an increase in the processing demands of the system, the API was scheduled to poll SMS messages from the modem at intervals.

Fig.1: Architecture of the proposed system

android platform. The SMS platform and e-voting platform enables electoral process by using electronic devices which is more secured

3. SYSTEM DESIGN

The entire architecture of our proposed system is built on four (4) major items components namely:

Fig.2: Program flowchart

3.1 The voters GSM phone

This is a personal phone of the voter. It is containing a SIM card registered with the Nigeria Communication Commission (NCC); and also, registered against a particular voter during the voters' registration. Each interested SMS voter is required to have unique registered SIM card.

3.2 GSM network

This is a cellular network on which GSM communication runs and where SMS messages are held up for specified amount of time till they are delivered to their intended numbers. Each target area of SMS voting is required to have GSM network coverage.

3.3 The application server

This is the computer system running the SMS voting application; the SMS API; and hosting the voters' database peculiar to that unit. The SMS

API is scheduled to pull SMS messages from each of the modem connected to it. After retrieving the message, this message is passed to the SMS voting application to confirm the correctness of the format; to confirm that the number is voting a particular position for the first time and to log the vote in the database against the number when all the confirmations returns successful.

3.4 The GSM modem

Following the levels of government in Nigeria, each local government area (LGA) is designed to have a specific number. This device will help the system to handle the network load; as well as to easily poll the result for each local government. The different GSM modems are plugged to application server and voters are required to send their submissions to their respective LGA's number. Both the application server and the modems are kept in the data centers.

The entire process takes four (4) phases. In the first phase, the voter sends a message to a particular number in order to gain access to vote for any position and a candidate of his/her choice. Secondly, a feedback of different positions is displayed on the voter's screen. Here, the voter selects the position he/she wants to vote for and then move to the next phase of the system. Thirdly, the list of the valid contestants is displayed to the voter's phone as feedback. The voter selects the candidates he/she wants to vote for and click on send. Finally, an acknowledgement notification is sent to the voter on the success of his or her vote (See Fig.2).

Voters List

SMS voting

Result

Contestants List

Fig 3: Proposed SMS voting model

Fig 4: User Interface

In other to provide storage for the system, a database management tool (most preferred) was used. The tool selected for our study is mySQL. Our proposed system makes use of the following tables: contestants table, voters table, and election table. The voters list and the contestants list will provide the input of the system while the result will serve as the output of the system (See Fig.3).

4. SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

Our system was implemented using VB.NET programming language and GSMCOMM API. Some factors were considered before this particular programming language and component was chosen, such factor includes:

1. Visual Basic .NET (VB.NET) is a multi-paradigm, object-oriented programming language, implemented on the .NET Framework.
2. Support of legacy keywords – Although some keywords have either been discontinued or their usages completely changed there still remains a huge amount of support of legacy keywords; this is useful for converting legacy projects to the current language specifications. Many will say that the VB.Net conversion wizard has many pitfalls; this is true, however, it does provide a starting point in the conversion process that many other languages do not provide.
3. Easy to use Rapid Application Design (RAD) interface – Within a matter of minutes a complete Graphical User Interface (GUI) can be produced; thus requiring less programming time and less design time.
4. Project wizards – When creating a new project, or just adding a new form or button, the environment will automatically generate the default coding to have the objects appear; in some cases there are wizards that can provide default

coding to have some functionality within the application. This translates to a working application can be designed and coded in a fraction of time than some other languages.

5. CONCLUSION

This project was initiated due to the inadequacies of the existing system, elections are rigged, legitimate voters are disenfranchised, the speed, accuracy, security and efficiency of the paper-based system is poor and there is very little privacy. The provision of an SMS-based voting system will improve users' participation and will also improve the efficiency and accuracy in information processing.

However adequate power supply is required to stage a running application server; each intended area is expected to have GSM network coverage; and each voter is required to have a uniquely registered SIM card. Also, the government should have the will power and the legislation needed to implement a workable system.

Further studies can be channelled to providing security to the data and the system and standardization of the system

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